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Learners' Perception toward a Mother-Tongue-Tutor living with Disability : An Ethnographic Study of Magar Community

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Abstract

A person's perception toward another person depends on his/her background as well as the background of another person. Disability is also a condition or situation of a particular person. Normal person's perception towards the persons with disability can be positive or negative but, in case of Nepalese society, it is conditional due to their caste/ethnicity, profession/occupation, and educational level, socioeconomic status, relationship to each-other, ideology and belief and so on. This article discusses on the perception of mother-tongue students (pupils without any kind of disability) in regards of their mother-tongue tutor – a male Magar living with physical disability. This article has been prepared based on the findings of an ethnographic study. The study shows that the learners' perception toward their mother-tongue tutor is different (both negative and positive) that depends on various factors—broadly, the sociocultural, educational and economic. The perception would be more positive and seems the potentialities (capabilities) in the persons with disabilities if the level of their education is higher, otherwise vice versa. Positive perception towards the person with disability also creates self-motivation for students and their learning. The research findings have been analyzed in the view of Sen's Capability Theory.

Key words: Perception, Disability, language students, Tutor with physical disability, Magar.

Introduction

The term "Disability" is considered as a difficult situation that exists as a long-term physical, mental, intellectual or sensory impairments, functional impairment or barriers and

that may hinder their full and effective participation in social life on an-equal basis with other. The Disability World (2020) defines a 'disability' as a condition or function judged to be significantly impaired relative to the usual standard of an individual or group (www.disabled-world.com/disability). On one hand, there may be effects on organs or body parts so that that might be somehow difficulties to function and work in their daily life. On the other hand, either they feel weaker themselves due this difficulties as well as social structure or the societal discrimination based on that. Ultimately, this situation creates constraints in their participation from individual level (e.g. in family) to society and the national level in broader sense.

The Disable World has categorized the "Disability" in eight broad sub-categories, which include 'Mobility and Physical Impairments', 'Spinal Cord Disability (injured lifelong due to accidents like that)', 'Head Injuries/Brain Disability or intellectual', 'Vision Disability', 'Hearing Disability', 'Cognitive or Learning Disabilities', 'Psychological Disorders' and 'Invisible Disabilities (medical)'. Regarding the population of the persons with disability (PWD), the same organization's record shows that:

Currently around 1.3 billion population (i.e. 16 percent) of the total world's population are living with a disability - they are experiencing and facing disabled situation. According to the UN Development Program (UNDP), 80 percent of persons with disabilities live in global south (developing countries). The World Bank estimates that 20 percent of the world's poorest people have some kind of disability, and tend to be regarded in their own communities as the most disadvantaged (WHO, 2023).

The National population survey held in 2021 shows total 647,744 population of persons with disability (PwDs) that 2.2 percent population of Nepal (CSO, 2023). However, considering the reports of World Health Organization (WHO) and the World Bank, the organizations of indigenous peoples living with

disability of Nepal claim that the population of indigenous peoples living with disability (IPwDs) is 1.3 million (NIDA et.al. 2018). If we consider this figure, the population of Magars living with disability is more than 5 lakhs. PwDs are human beings and members of the society.

Every individual sees and understands them in his/her own way, behave or interact in his/her own personal lens. Simply, this view is said perception. Oxford Advanced Student's Dictionary of Current English (2007) defines the term 'perception' as 'an idea, a belief or an image that a person sees or understands something' (Hornby, 2007, p. 1122). Other peoples without disabilities and PwDs themselves may have own perception towards the PwD. A survey research that done in UK in 2009 shows that almost 8 out of 10 respondents felt that there is either a lot or a little prejudice towards disabled people (Staniland, 2011, p. 9). Different people's perception towards the people with disability (PwD) might be different. There are so many factors like socio structure, beliefs, cultural, educational etc. based on which, people's perception are guided.

This article discusses the perception of the mother-tongue learners (who were without disability) towards their mother-tongue tutor (native teacher) who is physical disability (TWD). Both language students and Tutor belong to the Magar community. I (the author) conducted an ethnographic study to know the perception or theorize how the Nepali society sees, believes and understands a TWD. This article has been prepared based on study of the theoretical concepts, and review of the relevant literature and secondary data.

Research Methods

Under the non-positivistic research paradigm, I (author of this article) applied ethnographic research approach for this study. I selected a differently able person, who is a tutor of his mother tongue (Magar *Dhut* language). As a tutor, he takes class of his mother tongue at a 'language institute' of capital city Kathmandu. Some popular qualitative methods such as observation, interview and discussion were used to gather the required information. The

total number of the students is 44 (equal number of males and females) (please, refer the table-1). Individual interview (both formal and informal) was conducted with 30 students of Magar language and some staff of the institute and public. Besides, discussions were held with some of them in small groups (male youths and female home-makers).

Table-1: Distribution of the participants by sex and occupation.

SN	Language Students			Externals		Total
	College/schools students	School teachers	Home makers	Institute's Staff	Public	
Male	10	4	0	3	5	22
Female	8	2	6	1	5	22
Total	18	6	6	4	10	44

Source: Field work, September 2024.

Brief Profile of the Magar Language Tutor with Disability (TWD)

Kamal Bahadur (pseudonym), popularly known as KB sir, is 45 years aged male. He belongs to Magar community, the largest ethnic communities of Nepal. He is permanent resident of a rural village of Ilam district and from ex-Indian army family. He has completed intermediate level (I.Ed. with Major English) was completed from public college of Kathmandu. Since last 25 years he lives with his family (wife and 2 children) in Kathmandu. Now, his daughter studies in Bachelor level and son studies in grade 12 – in a boarding school. Kamal was an English teacher in a boarding school of Kathmandu and taught for 12 years. In a bike accident (in 2002), his lower level spinal was injured and then below the waist part became a disabled (called spinal disability or physical disability). Thereafter, he became well but his physical condition was changed permanently as a person with physical disability (popularly known as a “wheel-chair-user”). Then, he loosed not only his existing teaching job but never got opportunity of any kind of job to the date. But, due to his excellent command in both English and Mother-tongue (Magar-Dhut), later on, he generated an opportunity himself to serve home tuition to the school children and teaching Magar-language

to the interested learners especially youths and housewives who belong Magar indigenous community and were of his nearby location.

As a social worker and associated with different level of Magar's Associations, he envisioned to contribute to promote own mother-tongue (Magar language) in city-area and started to teach in the collaboration with a Language Institute in 2007 and collect a nominal fee. He teaches Mother tongue (*Magar Dhut*) in a 'language institute' as a part-time-job, although it is not regular - it depends on request of the students (who are interested to learn mother tongue). This is also a source of family income. Now, his wife is working in grocery super market, however she was jobless and preparing for teaching license when Kamal faced an expected bike-accident. The basic level course of this language is taught daily one hour for a 3-month's period of time. The numbers of students ranges 7 – 12 in a class and it run up to 2 shifts in a season but half of the year – in rainy season and festival times, language classes are vacant run only if the interested students come and join. Occasionally, Mr Magar serves as a trainer of Magar-tongue teaching for Magar-tongue teachers of public schools where Mother tongue is taught in lower graders. For this purpose, he visits different regions of the country.

Theoretical Framework

British Social Attitudes Surveys (2009), which was carried out nationwide in UK by using two methods (face-to-face and anonyms questionnaire surveys), shows that 85 percent respondents expressed their positive views towards the PwDs whereas same views was expressed by the 77 percent respondents in the previous survey held in 2005. Survey shows that still 17 percent respondents (without disability) felt discomfort and awkward with PwDs – that is called the negative perception. It was also found that the general public's perception towards peoples depends upon the nature of the disability. Their perception towards persons with physical and sensory impairment was found more positive than persons with other

types of disabilities like learning disabilities, mental health conditions (Stanil, 2011, p. 47).

A literature based study, done by F. Hannon (2006) on behalf of National Disability Authority, Ireland, on attitudes towards disability shows that differences in people's response were found according to sex, age and social class. Negative attitude to disability persists there was improving in Ireland and worldwide (Hannon, 2006 p. 3). The study shows that a clear relationship between attitudes and personal experience of disability was found in both the 2001 and 2006 national surveys in the Republic of Ireland as well as in many other studies worldwide. Negative attitude towards PwDs indicates that they are still not fully integrated within the society and that can slow progress towards equality.

Based on review of literature pertaining to Sen's Capability Theory, Sharma (2005) has analyzed the constructs of this theory and redefined for implication in disability and rehabilitation research. Five constructs (exchange entitlements, characteristics, capabilities, functioning and well-being) of this theory have been identified, defined and described. Based on this, capabilities of the PwDs can be seen and analyzed from the externals' (who are without disability) view. Moreover, descriptive studies can be undertaken to explain and predict the extent of well-being in persons with disabilities based on this paradigm and using these constructs as predictors (Sharma, 2005, p. 129). It is important contribution to see the disability issue in capabilities perspective. Besides, through this angle peoples' perception can be understood. But it is not clear that from whose perspective capabilities constructs should be seen and measured (PwDs' self or only of non-disabled or of both).

A research done by the Scottish Executive in 2005 shows that the decision to employ a person with learning disabilities and or autistic spectrum disorders (ASD) was influenced by several factors including the professionalism; the tendency of the company; labor shortages; reliable gain and consistent workers etc. (the Scottish Executive, 2005). If the employers see the more gain and there is shortage of laborers in the market then recruit

this sort of peoples. It means, their perception towards the PwDs is somehow positive but it depends on the returns and opportunity cost. The study has pointed out the inconsistency of national framework of employment which prevailed as the biggest barrier for ensuring their employment and that framework influenced the employers to perceive the potential employees who are with disabilities. Role of the family, their background, social construct are important factors, based on that identity of the PwDs is recognized and ignored, and that ultimately influence in employers' decision making to employ the laborers with disabilities. Research did not investigate these aspects that were important to analyze in this study.

Research done by Altai Consulting (2004) in three regions (central, southern and western region) of Afghanistan (by using in-depth questionnaire survey focus group discussion and case study methods) shows that perception towards PwDs depends on economic status, position in the family, education level, age and gender of the PwDs. The people's belief is that '*mayubiat*' (who are disabled by birth) who are most stigmatized, causes strongly rooted to culture and folklore (linked religious and spiritual beliefs) and they express more sympathy and respect for '*mayubiat*'. However there is more hope and expectations associated with '*maluliat*' (who became disabled in lifetime). This is more positive perception. Society and PwDs themselves think they do not have the capacity and the ability to work. Even family's perception towards the members with disability was found negative that was guided by the social structure particularly religious and spiritual beliefs. People's attitudes vary for different types of disabilities: mental/intellectual disabilities stigmatized the most (it is considered the worst); visual impairment the least (p. 27); more indifference towards and isolation of disabled women, especially having visual disability. Prevalent negative attitudes exist (verbal abuse and indifference) within society against PwDs. The research concludes that disability is a social phenomenon in Afghanistan. Research has also recommended the ways for changing perception towards

PwDs. Comparison with other countries' context has not been made. It would be better if it would have been done.

The findings of the 2002 National Scottish Social Attitudes Survey showed that attitudes towards disability in Scotland are little affected by social characteristics such as age, class and education, or even by their own experience of disability. The findings also showed that someone's economic position did not influence their attitude towards PwDs (www.scotland.gov.uk/library5/society).

The National Centre for Social Research, Britain (2002) undertook a study to examine the peoples' attitudes towards, and experiences of, disability. Mixed method was used in this study (interview, group discussions and face-to-face survey with PwDs and non-disabilities). The study shows that people's (who are without disability) perception towards the PwDs depends on time onset of disability, nature of the disability and extent of involvement in groups. General people's perception was found both positive and negative. The negative perception was that PwDs lose the level of physical or mental ability, and that in turn, lose their independence and increase dependency upon others for key personal activities such as dressing, using the toilet and eating. Many normal peoples, who were in direct contact or with experience with PwDs, expressed more negative perception towards PwDs. In contrast, some normal people who have indirect experience with PwDs were positive about the potential for living a full life with a disability. In their perception, PwDs are able to develop alternative capabilities to counteract their disability and can lead happy, fulfilling lives (Grewal, Joy, Lewis, Swales, & Woodfield, 2002, p. 51). A significant minority of people felt that the portrayal of disabled people in the media was negative. It was felt that the fictional media was less positive than factual media because the media did not portray their normal lives and a lack of visibility (ibid, p. 60). In Britain, two national level surveys had already been done (in 1998 and 2000) and some interventions have been made from the government side for improving the condition of the PwDs and raising awareness of

the public. It would have been better if the situation could have been compared.

From the aforementioned review of relevant literature, I came to know that general peoples' perception towards the PwDs might be both positive and negative. Perception of attitude cannot be measured but it is obvious. Besides, there are various factors that play significant role in determining peoples' perception towards the PwDs. A perception does not depend on only one aspect solely. However, social constructs are found more influencing factors to determine peoples' perception. Thus, in ethnographic study, I tried to see the peoples' (language students called students in this study) perception towards a PwD (called the language tutor in this study) more in social perspective and concentrating on social phenomena. This is social model of disability (Capton & Fitzgerald, 2012) and peoples' perception is looking in this lens. So that this study has been done in qualitative methods and research findings have been analyzed and interpreted in such way [not in other ways like medical/genetic model or right-based model of disability, as mentioned by Capton & Fitzgerald (2012)].

Research Findings

Perception is changed over time

In this ethnographic study, I found that all language students were not aware on disability issues and no sensitive so far before to meet their KB sir (tutor – Kamal). They did not care and think about the disability. According to them, before to meet the tutor, they thought that 'disability' was not issue/subject of concern for them and that was unnecessary matter for them; they have no responsibility towards the PwDs. When they interacted with KB sir and knew about him and his disability then their perception was gradually changed. One of the major reasons behind that was they had got chance to interact with PwDs and understand about their life. In this regards, one of the youth lady students said,

"I had seen and met many PwDs but I had never talked to them, never thought

about them and their life, never talked with other peoples, even with my collage's friends, about the disability, PwDs and their life. I never thought 'disability as a social issue'. I never thought 'how it happens'. But, when I got an opportunity to read a book written by him (the tutor) then I knew little bit about him and the cause of his disability. Thereafter, I didn't feel so surprise when I met him first time in language class."

In the beginning classes, all students had curiosity to know about the background of KB sir as a disability and his family life, but nobody asked him directly about the reasons of his disability and his daily life.

Different perceptions on financial status

Livelihood of the KB sir is one of the major concerns of the students (who are normal and never faced any kind of disability). One of the adult female students expressed her view:

"In the initial classes, we had curiosity to know – how he became disabled and who are in his family, how he is sustaining (livelihood of his family), where are his relatives and do they support him or not? But we could not ask. Later on, he shared his history all about."

There is no doubt, general people feel comfortable when s/he meet and interact with PwDs. But even later, some of them feel awkward. A survey done in Britain in 2002 shows that more than 1 in 4 peoples felt uncomfortable in an encounter with a deaf person (hearing disability) and in same portion of peoples wanted to avoid an encounter with someone experiencing mental illness (intellectual/learning disability) (Grewal, Joy, Lewis, Swales, & Woodfield, 2002, p. 29). It was observed that the learners' perception was changed over time. Initially, students felt uneasy to talk more with the tutor because of fear of 'what he thinks' or 'can this pinch him'. But gradually, they felt easy and interacted

more focused on the subject matter/course and little bit on tutor's personal matter when he used to share his experiences. It is also found that perception towards PwDs also depends on the age, social norms and values, profession, gender, economic status.

In my own experience, generally normal persons have negative perception towards PwDs. I have got opportunities to serve for the NGOs of the PwDs through delivering trainings, supporting their organizational policies and evaluating their projects. Then, I have seen that economic condition of most of the PwDs and their families is poor or just surviving. On one hand, they are dependent with other members of the family for survival because of their physical difficulties and, on the other hand, understanding of the other peoples is that they can't do anything for family and him too. And, neither the alternative ways to involve the PwDs in economic activities and/or to empower them economically are given nor searched for. In this study, I found two different perceptions, viz. more positive and somehow negative. Adult females were more serious about the tutor's survival/livelihood. It was seen as being more generous towards him. They were also ready to support him financially. One of the female students expressed that:

“When we knew about his family and livelihood then that makes us unhappy and hurt us. I am worry on ‘how he is surviving’. So I often say him to ask me without feeling uncomfortable if he need any financial support (e.g. for paying children's school fees, purchasing medicines).

This also indicates that, learners' perception, their tutor is financially poor or he is not so capable to earn enough for survival of his family. Disability of the tutor was considered as an objective concept and means that aspects of a person's body do not function or function with difficulty (Crow, 1996 as cited in Grewal, Joy, Lewis, Swales, & Woodfield, 2002, p. 27). As I understood, one of the reasons behind this is economic status of the students. The economic status (earning) of the families of

those students who expressed this kind of view was sound (they were British armies' families).

Occupation and Education determine Individual's perception

Those students who were teachers expressed different view in this regard. They did not underestimate him. In their view, he is equal to them. If opportunity is provided then he can earn because he has knowledge, skills and idea. One of the students, he is also one of the promoters of the same language institute, gave a logical example in such a way,

“When KB sir came to us and requested to provide an opportunity to teach tuition to the children or English language, and then shared his experiences and idea. Then I tried to recognize his knowledge and skills and also realized to give him an opportunity to run this class (mother tongue). Then, I talked to a sister (who had already learnt this language with same tutor) and we combine sponsored first session/batch. Then, he created an idea to collect fund by celebrating ‘Deusi-Bhailo’ and teaching to the college students in nominal fees. Then, we all supported him. Now, these sessions are running from that collected fund, and we are providing space- classroom and some necessary materials in free of cost from our side.”

This finding is more compatible with the findings of other research carried out in abroad, for instance – survey done in Afghanistan in 2004 (Altai Consulting, 2004), Scotland in 2002 (www.scotland.gov.uk/library5/society), UK in 2006 (Hannon, 2006, p. 13) show that economic status of the people is also one of the factors to determine their perception towards PwDs.

Gender perception

Likewise, some of the mother-tongue learners' perception towards their tutor was seen somehow from the gender's perspective. No one expressed in words but it could be observed and analyzed from their other interaction. For example, the adult female students who were home-makers emphasized on his role (overall role) as a male-head in the family. This emphasis to role, according to the "Role theory", he has to perform (Biddle, 1986, p. 67). In such a way we can say that this is somehow negative perception towards the tutor and one-way perspective to looking at the disability which is conventional in Nepali context.

Individual's Profession and Level of Education does matter to perceive

Similarly, the mother-tongue learners' perception towards their native tutor also found different that was based on their education and understanding level, and their professions/occupations. If the academic level of those learners is higher (e.g. college level) as compared to the tutor, and they are by teachers (private sector) by profession and college students then their level of understanding was found higher (wider) and liberal as compared to those whose education level is just school's level and are home-makers/housewives. The first groups did not underestimate the capacity (except physical) of their tutor – KB sir.

They believed that the tutor is equally capable like them, and in some cases he is more capable and competent than other. They gave some examples, which were: he has good social networks, he is leading a couple of social organizations (related to disability and his mother tongue), he had experiences of trainers and worked for a long time as a social worker, he creates literature etc.). In these cases, they accepted themselves weaker than him. This implies that these learners' perception was positive towards the tutor and his ability. This view is definitely somehow new and more concentrated on the tutor's internal ability rather than physical and daily livelihood.

However, the second group expressed their perception towards the tutor by focusing on his physical ability, performance in daily life and his overall role and responsibilities that has to

fulfill in his family as a family-head. In their view, they did not find him as other males are. It was gender lens by which their little bit negative perception was expressed. But in case of younger lady students did not present this kind of view and behavior.

Some of the findings of research done in other countries are matched with these findings but some of the findings are found just opposite. For examples, an old survey done in Britain had shown that those respondents with higher levels of education had more positive perception or attitudes towards PwDs than those respondents with lower levels of education (Grewal, Joy, Lewis, Swales, & Woodfield, 2002, p. 11). This finding was matched. But, as shown by the same survey, those respondents with higher incomes, women and public sector employees had more positive attitudes towards PwDs than those respondents with lower incomes, men and private sector employees respectively (Grewal, Joy, Lewis, Swales, & Woodfield, 2002, p. 11). This finding was just opposite to the finding of this ethnographic research. The reasons behind this kind of differences might be socio-cultural aspects.

I tried to see their behavior by observing their daily interaction and activities when they meet for language class. I observed that male students pushed his wheelchair for entering in and exist from the class room without asking for support. Because of inaccessible construction of a toilet at institute, he does not enter there but male students used to take away a bottle of his urine and pour at toilet without feeling uncomfortable. They were supporting him in his this sort of daily life activities by accepting as a support. As observed by the outsiders (like shopkeepers), this kinds of activities and behavior was common, neither they heard anything against their tutor nor noticed anything done for him without interest. In the 2006 Survey on Public Attitudes to Disability, 55% of respondents thought that PwDs were treated fairly in Irish society whereas earlier surveys carried out by the DRC Britain (2000) and DRC Scotland (2001) found that 50% of respondents considered that PwDs were treated fairly (Grewal, Joy, Lewis, Swales, & Woodfield, 2002, p.

16). The important aspect here is acceptance. If the students accepted the tutor (PwD) then their behavior became normal and special too as per need.

Hierarchy and relationship determine Individual's perception

Certainly, there was hierarchal relationship between the students and the tutor while they were in teaching-learning. But, thereafter they were found as members of a same family. Similarly, all students and tutor were from same ethnic community and language teaching-learning could be a way to unite all of them culturally as well as emotionally. This thing also played significant role to think about the tutor in more positive way. This was also one of the influencing factors to determine an individual's perception towards the PwDs.

From the interaction with the students, I explored one important aspect, which is related to their learning and motivation. Because of the getting information about the tutor (his disability, life, struggle, achievements and self-motivation, confidence and strong desire etc.), almost all students are inspired. Everyone is giving importance that class and committed to learn. Some of the students (especially youths –both male & female) are self-motivated to learn and have strong desire to teach other in future. One of the leady says,

“I am really inspired from KB sir's struggle and his desire to do something for our community - 'Ma pani kehi garna sakchhu ra mero samudayako ladi maile kehi garnu parchha'. I want to help KB sir. Ss a student myself, I can't do so something. But, I am thinking that I would learn this language well and, in future, I want to teach to others who want to learn mother tongue. He will have to face transportation problem to go far from his locality. So, I am thinking to take part in supporting in his path. Let see.”

Similarly, a male youth student expressed his view,

“I had no problem to write and speak mother tongue but I wanted to know the grammatical matters, which has been taught me by KB sir. He is heartily guiding me. I want to train our school teachers (who teach mother tongue in the district) for teaching effectively. I hope I can do.”

It has proved that teachers' attitudes towards students with disabilities have a significant impact on the educational experience (Kenny et al, 2000 as cited in Lodge and Lynch 2004, p. 22).

Changed positive perception becomes motivational factor

In this research, it was also found that positive attitude or behavior of the tutor with disability motivated the students without disabilities for learning. When researcher also discussed with the tutor about the learning of the learners then it was found that those students are more committed, they have set their learning goals and learning accordingly. Here, the tutor's behavior became an important factor not only in learning and educational achievement but also, based on which, the learners' perception was determined. Ultimately, the learners' positive perception created self-motivation/inspiration for effective learning. Researcher analyzed that when they were impressed then they started to see him in more positive way although they were not so negative from very beginning. To some extent, it is significant in influencing the general peoples' perception towards PwDs. But for this, interaction between PwD and person without disability is necessary. Interactions provide the opportunities to understand each other and making own perception toward other.

Discussion

This study focused to the mother-tongue learners' perception towards the tutor and seeing this in social aspects (which is called social model of disability, according to Capton & Fitzgerald (2012). It seems the perception and relationship

between the tutor and learner of mother-tongue is not only the sociolinguistics aspect but also the psycholinguistics aspect. Social construct was found stronger than other. The researcher came to in a conclusion that the general peoples' perception also depends on the behaviour of their tutors, and that might be positive and straight relationship. The researcher tried to analyze the findings (learners' perception) in the perspective of Amartya Sen's Capability Theory. So that this section is devoted to discuss the learners' perception towards their mother-tongue tutor (PwD) – by seeing capabilities of the tutor in his learners' lens not of himself.

Sen's Capability theory and Perception towards PwDs

The mother-tongue learners' perception can be linked with the Sen's capability theory in the context of the language tutor – KB sir (PwD). There are two different perceptions – positive and negative. Five constructs of the Sen's capability theory are: Exchange entitlements, Characteristics, Capabilities, Functioning and Well-being. As defined by Sharma (2005), exchange entitlements are goods and services that are obtained from a person's resources other than through production and sale, and it can be applied to identify the PwDs who assist with functional independence and identify goods and services useful for themselves that can be obtained (Sharma, 2005, p. 128). Income and other available resources can be considered. In this regards, everyone student accepted that these entitlements are very limited with tutor's family that is hardly sufficient for survival of his family. In this theoretical sense, learners' perception was that the tutor is living under the required capability condition.

Sharma (2005) defines another construct of the capability theory, i.e. 'characteristics' as a commodity or good that is valued, and it is used to identify the values for goods and services utilized by the PwDs (Sharma, 2005, p. 128). This can be understood in term of quality of goods and services utilized by the PwDs. In this regards, the learners' perception would not be directly concerned with the tutor. But, they would make own

view about the tutor based on the goods and services that he used. In specific way, they could not say anything about him but they generalized in such a way that he and his family is consuming same quality- goods and services whatever most of the Nepali use. It means, they wouldn't like to underestimate (not negative view).

Another construct of the Sen's capability theory is 'capabilities', which are things a person can achieve or could have achieved in life based on real opportunities (Sharma, 2005, p. 129). These are linked with many things/aspects of human life, e.g. physical health, life expectancy, mental health, being a part of society, having friends, freedom to pursue education, freedom to pursue career, freedom to be mobile, freedom to have job and so on. The students think that the tutor is one of socially excluded persons by the society because of his disability but he is accepted and respected within his community and among the learners' groups including institute's staffs. No one feels awkward and does discriminatory or dominating behavior towards him. They accepted that he is a part of the society, he is equal to them but he should get more privileges than other. This view indicates the rights, recognition, equality, dignity, social justice of the PwDs and acceptance of diversity (Grewal, Joy, Lewis, Swales, & Woodfield, 2002, p. 28).

Functioning is a mixture of "doings and beings" or the various options or actions we perform in everyday life to achieve things in life (Sharma, 2005, p. 129). In this aspect, the learners' perception towards PwDs was found both in 'for' and 'against'. More positive perception was expressed by those students who were more educated (studying or passed collage level). They saw that there are several options to achieve things for their tutor. In their view, he can 'do and be' like other peoples without disabilities 'do and be'. For example, he is knowledgeable person and expert of his mother tongue; he has written books both in mother tongue and Nepali, he also creates literature in both languages. From this kind of efforts, he can earn; his social status will upgrade; he can contribute to the society; he can reach in a leading position. They shared an example that was – he is

teaching them and leading two organizations (one related to disability and another related to his mother tongue).

On the other hand, some students, who were economically sound, female-house-makers, educationally at low, elder than other, expressed somehow doubt that indicates the tutor's low capabilities. That focused more to economic, movement and dependency for living every-day life. It was seen completely from Nepali societal lenses – particularly patriarchy and masculinity, which implies he has main responsibility to fulfill the needs of the family and he must be a '*purus*' (a capable male/hero) – but it is not possible. A survey carried out in Afghanistan showed that society and PwDs themselves think that they do not have the capacity and the ability to work (Altai Consulting, 2004, P. 52). The survey further showed that even family's perception towards the members with disability was found negative that was guided by the social structure particularly religious and spiritual. Not only in other's context but also even in our context, we can say that, this is also stereotype thinking of the society. Indeed, the students compared the status of the tutor with their own and judge his capabilities accordingly.

The final construct of the capability theory is well-being. Well-being refers to one's own welfare and it includes a getting goods and services one wants, feeling of satisfaction, and self-perceived health (Sharma, 2005, p. 129). In this matter, the students expressed their view only based on their assumption. For example, they believed that the tutor could not get any special privileges. But, they know his experiences (both affirmative and discriminatory treatment done by other). Based on that, they understood that he was not satisfied at all with other's behavior (except some cases). But, regarding his own efforts and success of life, they felt that he is really satisfied. As they understood, he has been contributing to his community and some peoples have been helping him by heart. In their own judgment, he was not getting well-being from outsiders – particularly by the state, his community's organizations in comparison to his contribution in the community.

A survey done in Britain shows that one-third of people believed that PwDs cannot lead a full life due to their health problems (Grewal, Joy, Lewis, Swales, & Woodfield, 2002, p. 29). The survey result further depicts that 1 in 5 people believe that in general PwDs cannot be as effective at work as their non-disabled colleagues. In capabilities perception, PwD's capabilities are weakened due to his/her disability. Based on the aforementioned discussion, my understanding is that the capability of a person especially PwD is seen in different angles. There are different perceptions and attitudes of the people, even students/pupils perception towards their tutor who is with disability. There are various factors based on which people's perception is set or made. People's social constructs like caste/ethnicity, gender, norms and values, hierarchy, role etc.; economic factors like earning, resources etc.; profession related factor like types of occupation; education related factor like level of understanding, academic achievement, and so on.

It was found that multiple factors combine to set a person's perception. Not only educational or occupational or economic but also mixed of all played a role in combined form to set perception. For instance, those students who were house-makers, adult, female, economic status was sound but education was comparatively lower than other students expressed their perception that their tutor (TwD) has many problems, he can hardly solve these problems and need to be supported (i.e. less capability) whereas those students who are youths, teachers/college students, economically little bit in lower position, influenced by modernization (technologically) expressed their perception in just opposite to the previous group (i.e. the tutor was differently able and can do and be like other, and some context better than other too). This indicates that in capability perspective the tutor has capabilities.

Conclusion

From this study it was explored that the students do not care the tutor (PwD) until they know the reason of his disability. When they were informed about the tutor's background then they

become more conscious about this issue and their perception also gradually changes (from negative to positive) over time. If we see the disability issue from social model (as prescribed by Capton & Fitzgerald (2012), then we can find that the peoples' perception depends on the social constructs like social norms and values, roles, gender, economic status, social relationship etc. Similarly, the general peoples' perception towards the PwDs may differ and that also depends based on the level of their education and understanding, and their professions/occupations.

When the researcher analyzed the learners' view towards the tutor based on five constructs of the Sen's capability theory in his context then it was found that their perceptions were different (both negative and positive). I arrived at conclusion that individual's perception depends on various factors –mainly sociocultural, educational and economic (even in this rank). Social construct was found stronger than other. For example, being members of same ethnic community, all learners' perception toward the tutor was seen more positive. Another crucial factor is education that widens the individual's view and their perception is determined accordingly. Their perception would be more positive and see the potentialities (capabilities) in the PwDs if their education level is higher and vice versa. In short, the general peoples judge and assume the capabilities of the PwDs based on their own socioeconomic and education background and level.

Likewise, I came to in another conclusion, that is, the general peoples' perception also depends on a PwD's behaviour. There is positive and straight relationship or if a PwD positively treats the persons without disabilities then, as a result, their perception would be positive toward him/her. In addition, positive perception towards the PwDs creates self-motivation for learning and learning achievement.

Implications

This ethnographic research was conducted in short time period and explored the language learners' (pupils') perception towards their tutor (who was with physical disabilities), and

based on which general peoples' perception towards the PwDs was explored in Nepali context. However, there are other kinds of disabilities (like intellectual, visual, hearing, speech etc.) and the peoples' perception might be different according to variability of the disabilities. Other research done in abroad (e.g. survey done in Britain in 2002 & 2009; in Scotland in 2005) have shown the different perceptions and attitudes of the respondents according to the disabilities and their own background like socioeconomic, educational, professional and so on. It was important to study to know the peoples' perception toward the different disabilities. Similarly, this study only focused on language learners' (who were without disabilities) perception toward their tutor (PwD) from the same ethnic community – the Magar community, but it was not incorporated the view of other PwDs and his family members and/or dears, colleagues relatives. Perception of an individual with/without disability condition as well as social relationship with PwDs may vary (which has been shown in a research done in Afghanistan in 2004), which is also important area of doing study in our context.

Findings of this study were analyzed in the perspective of the Sen's capability theory (capabilities of a PwD in the other's view), however it can be analyzed in other theoretical perspectives, for example, social role theory (how the respondents see PwD's role in the society), critical theory (how the disability is seen critically in relation to social construct) etc. Likewise, this study focused on the perception in view of the social model of disability however it can be seen in other models like medical/genetic model and right-based model of disability. This kind of study (might be triangulation) would explore multiple views of the society.

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